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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Learning Both Ends

Another day portraying the educator's role,
Reunited nurse-instructors toward one goal.
In the context of academe
Achievement is the main aim.

Synchronous sessions are preferred,
Online classes are accepted.
Not a single topic is missed,
In a regular day without rest.

A lot of students to assess,
Recruiting knowledge they possess.
A point in every test,
Surviving is the quest.

Adaptation to each clinical exposure
Nursing supervision is given without rigor.
Integrating theory and clinical competency
Empowering students with proficiency.

Learning has to be discerned,
In some aspects, this is a concern...
Lifelong understanding comes with no end...
Yearning for knowledge is both a teacher and a student strain...